

ON THE DEGREE OF REGULARITY OF GENERALIZED VAN DER WAERDEN TRIPLES

Jacob Fox

Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA 02139, USA

licht@mit.edu

Radoš Radoičić

Department of Mathematics, Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey, Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA

rados@math.rutgers.edu

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Abstract

Let a and b be positive integers such that $a \leq b$ and $(a, b) \neq (1, 1)$. We prove that there exists a 6-coloring of the positive integers that does not contain a monochromatic (a, b) -triple, that is, a triple (x, y, z) of positive integers such that $y = ax + d$ and $z = bx + 2d$ for some positive integer d . This confirms a conjecture of Landman and Robertson.

1. Introduction

In 1916, Schur [13] proved that for every finite coloring of the positive integers there is a monochromatic solution to $x + y = z$. In 1927, van der Waerden [15] proved that every finite coloring of the positive integers contains arbitrarily long monochromatic arithmetic progressions. Rado's 1933 thesis [12] was a seminal work in Ramsey theory, generalizing the earlier theorems of Schur and van der Waerden. Rado called a linear homogenous equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_nx_n = 0$ (a_i 's are nonzero integers) *r-regular* if every r -coloring of \mathbb{N} contains a monochromatic solution to that equation. An equation is *regular* if it is r -regular for all positive integers r . Rado's theorem for a linear homogeneous equation states that an equation is regular if and only if a non-empty subset of a_i 's sums to 0. Rado also made a conjecture [12] that further differentiates between those linear homogeneous equations that are regular and those that are not.

Conjecture 1 (*Rado's Boundedness Conjecture, 1933*) *For every positive integer n , there exists an integer $k := k(n)$ such that every linear homogeneous equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_nx_n = 0$ that is k -regular must be regular as well.*

This outstanding conjecture has remained open except in the trivial cases $(n = 1, 2)$ until recently, when the first author and Kleitman settled the first nontrivial case $n = 3$ [4], [9]. They proved that $k(3) \leq 24$.

Van der Waerden's theorem has been strengthened and generalized in numerous other ways [1], [2], [6], [7], [8], [11], [14]. In this note, we consider one of the generalizations, proposed by Landman and Robertson in [10].

Let a and b be positive integers such that $a \leq b$. A triple (x, y, z) of positive integers is called an (a, b) -triple if there exists a positive integer d such that $y = ax + d$ and $z = bx + 2d$. The *degree of regularity* of an (a, b) -triple, denoted by $\text{dor}(a, b)$, is the largest positive integer r , if it exists, such that for every r -coloring of the positive integers there is a monochromatic (a, b) -triple. If no such r exists, that is, for every finite coloring of the positive integers there is a monochromatic (a, b) -triple, then set $\text{dor}(a, b) = \infty$. Note that van der Waerden's theorem for 3-term arithmetic progressions is equivalent to $\text{dor}(1, 1) = \infty$.

Landman and Robertson proved that $\text{dor}(a, b) = 1$ if and only if $b = 2a$. They also showed that $\text{dor}(a, 2a - 1) = 2$ for $a \geq 2$. For small values of a and b , they provide few additional results:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dor}(1, 3) \leq 3, \text{dor}(2, 2) \leq 5, \text{dor}(2, 5) \leq 3, \text{dor}(2, 6) \leq 3, \\ \text{dor}(3, 3) \leq 5, \text{dor}(3, 4) \leq 5, \text{dor}(3, 8) \leq 3, \text{dor}(3, 9) \leq 3. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, they conjectured that if $(a, b) \neq (1, 1)$, then $\text{dor}(a, b)$ is finite [10], [11].

We confirm and further strengthen their conjecture.

Theorem 1 *If $(a, b) \neq (1, 1)$, then $\text{dor}(a, b) < 6$.*

Our proof that $\text{dor}(a, b)$ is finite uses Rado's theorem for a homogenous linear equation. Proving a specific upper bound of 6, regardless of parameters a and b , relies on the above mentioned proof of Fox and Kleitman [4].

2. Proof of Theorem 1

First, notice that if (x, y, z) is an (a, b) -triple, then (x, y, z) satisfies the equation

$$-(b - 2a)x - 2y + z = 0.$$

By Rado's theorem [12], this equation is regular if and only if $b \in \{2a - 2, 2a - 1, 2a + 1\}$. Therefore, if $b - 2a \notin \{-2, -1, 1\}$, then $\text{dor}(a, b)$ is finite. Moreover, since $k(3) \leq 24$ [4], if $b - 2a \notin \{-2, -1, 2\}$, then $\text{dor}(a, b) \leq 23$. As mentioned in the introduction, Landman and Robertson [10] proved that $\text{dor}(a, 2a - 1) = 2$ for $a \geq 2$.

For the remaining cases, we use Lemma 1, which is stated and proved next.

Lemma 1 *Let α and β be real numbers such that $1 < \alpha < \beta$. Set $r = \lceil \log_\alpha \beta \rceil$. Then every r -coloring of the positive integers contains integers x and y of the same color with $\alpha x \leq y \leq \beta x$. Moreover, there is an $(r + 1)$ -coloring of the positive integers that contains no integers x and y of the same color with $\alpha x \leq y \leq \beta x$.*

Proof. Consider a coloring of \mathbb{N} without x and y of the same color with $\alpha x \leq y \leq \beta x$. Since $r = \lceil \log_\alpha \beta \rceil$, then $\alpha^{r-1} < \beta$. Let $x_1 > \sum_{k=0}^{r-2} \alpha^k / (\beta - \alpha^{r-1})$ be a positive integer. For $i > 1$, set $x_{i+1} = \lceil \alpha x_i \rceil$. We have $\alpha x_i \leq x_{i+1} < \alpha x_i + 1$. Repeatedly using the inequality $x_{i+1} < \alpha x_i + 1$, we obtain $x_r < \alpha^{r-1} x_1 + \sum_{k=0}^{r-2} \alpha^k$. Since we appropriately chose x_1 , the last inequality yields $x_r < \beta x_1$. Hence, $\alpha x_i \leq x_j \leq \beta x_i$ for $1 \leq i < j \leq r$, so x_1, \dots, x_r must all have different colors. Therefore, the number of colors is at least $r + 1$.

Next, we construct a coloring of the positive integers by the elements of \mathbb{Z}_{r+1} such that there do not exist x and y of the same color with $\alpha x \leq y \leq \beta x$. For every nonnegative integer n , integers in the interval $[\alpha^n, \alpha^{n+1})$ receive color $n \pmod{r + 1}$. Within each interval, every pair of integers x and y have the same color, but $y < \alpha x$. For monochromatic x and y from different intervals, with $y > x$, we have $y > \alpha^r x \geq \beta x$. Therefore, this $(r + 1)$ -coloring of the integers has no monochromatic x and y such that $\alpha x \leq y \leq \beta x$. \square

Now, we continue with the proof of Theorem 1. We have two cases.

Case 1. $b = 2a + 1$.

In this case, we have $y = ax + d$ and $z = (2a + 1)x + 2d$. Therefore, $2y < z < (\frac{2a+1}{a})y$. Using Lemma 1 and noting $a \geq 1$, we obtain

$$\text{dor}(a, 2a + 1) \leq \lceil \log_2(2 + \frac{1}{a}) \rceil = 2.$$

Hence, for all positive integers a , we have $\text{dor}(a, 2a + 1) = 2$.

Case 2. $b = 2a - 2$.

Since b must be a positive integer, then $a \geq 2$. As mentioned in the introduction, Landman and Robertson [10] proved that $\text{dor}(2, 2) \leq 5$. If $a > 2$, then $y = ax + d$ and $z = (2a - 2)x + 2d$. So, $(\frac{2a-2}{a})y < z < 2y$. Using Lemma 1 and $a \geq 3$, we obtain

$$\text{dor}(a, 2a - 2) \leq \lceil \log_{2-\frac{2}{a}} 2 \rceil.$$

We have $2 - \frac{2}{a} > \sqrt{2}$ when $a > 3$. Therefore, $2 \leq \text{dor}(a, 2a - 2) \leq 3$ for $a = 3$ and $\text{dor}(a, 2a - 2) = 2$ for $a > 3$.

At this stage, we have $\text{dor}(a, b) < 24$, whenever $(a, b) \neq (1, 1)$. Next, we improve the upper bound using some sophisticated tools from the paper of Fox and Kleitman [4]. For the sake of completeness and clarity, we repeat some of their analysis that applies in our context. We need the following bit of notation.

Definition: Let p be a prime number. For every integer n , let $v_p(n)$ denote the largest power of p that divides n . If $n = 0$, let $v_p(n) = +\infty$.

Notice that $v_p(m_1 m_2) = v_p(m_1) + v_p(m_2)$ for every prime p , and integers m_1 and m_2 . The following straightforward lemma (Lemma 3 in [4]) gives basic properties of the function v_p , which we will repeatedly use.

Lemma 2 *If m_1, m_2, m_3 are integers with $v_p(m_1) \leq v_p(m_2) \leq v_p(m_3)$ and $v_p(m_1) < v_p(m_1 + m_2 + m_3)$, then $v_p(m_1) = v_p(m_2)$. Furthermore, if $v_p(m_3) < v_p(m_1 + m_2 + m_3)$, then also $v_p(m_1 + m_2) = v_p(m_3)$.*

Recall that if (x, y, z) is an (a, b) -triple, then (x, y, z) satisfies the equation $(b - 2a)x + 2y - z = 0$. Let $t_x = b - 2a$, $t_y = 2$, and $t_z = -1$ denote the coefficients of x , y , and z in this equation, respectively. We have three cases to consider, depending on t_x .

Case A. t_x is a multiple of 4.

Clearly, we have $v_2(t_x) > v_2(t_y) = 1 > v_2(t_z) = 0$. Let $S = \{v_2(t_x), v_2(t_y), v_2(t_x) - v_2(t_y)\}$, and let $\Gamma(S)$ be the undirected Cayley graph of the group $(\mathbb{Z}, +)$ with generators being the elements of S . Since every vertex of $\Gamma(S)$ has degree $2|S|$, there exists a proper (greedy) $(|S| + 1)$ -coloring χ' of its vertices. This result is “folklore” and we refer the reader to Lemma 2 in [4] for details. Now, define $\chi(n) = \chi'(v_2(n))$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We claim that in the 4-coloring χ of \mathbb{N} there are no x, y , and z , all of the same color and $v_2(t_x x + t_y y + t_z z) > \min\{v_2(t_x x), v_2(t_y y), v_2(t_z z)\}$. Indeed, otherwise (by Lemma 2) we have $v_2(t_x x) = v_2(t_y y)$; or $v_2(t_x x) = v_2(t_z z)$; or $v_2(t_y y) = v_2(t_z z)$. This implies $v_2(y) - v_2(x) = v_2(t_x) - v_2(t_y)$; or $v_2(z) - v_2(x) = v_2(t_x)$; or $v_2(z) - v_2(y) = v_2(t_y)$. However, this contradicts that χ' is a proper coloring of $\Gamma(S)$ and $v_2(x), v_2(y)$, and $v_2(z)$ are all of the same color.

Since $v_2(0) = +\infty$, by definition, and since there are no x, y, z , all of the same color and $v_2(t_x x + t_y y + t_z z) > \min\{v_2(t_x x), v_2(t_y y), v_2(t_z z)\}$, then, in particular, there are no monochromatic solutions to $t_x x + t_y y + t_z z = 0$ (i.e. $(b - 2a)x + 2y - z = 0$) in χ . Case A is equivalent to Lemma 4 (with $p = 2$) in [4].

Case B. t_x has an odd prime factor p .¹

In this case we have $v_p(t_x) > v_p(t_y) = v_p(t_z) = 0$. Let $d = v_p(t_x)$. We construct a 6-coloring χ that is a product of a 2-coloring χ_1 and a 3-coloring χ_2 . For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ define $\chi_1(n) \equiv \lfloor \frac{v_p(n)}{d} \rfloor \pmod{2}$. The coloring $\chi_1(n)$ colors intervals of v_p values of length d , open on one side, periodically in 2 colors with period 2. Let Γ be the undirected Cayley graph on $\mathbb{Z}_p \setminus \{0\}$ such that (u, v) is an edge of Γ if and only if $u - 2v \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ or $2u - v \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Since every vertex of Γ has degree 2, there exists a proper 3-coloring $\chi_2 : V(\Gamma) \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ define $\chi_2(n) = \chi_2(m \bmod p)$, where $n = mp^{v_p(n)}$. Finally, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ define $\chi(n) = (\chi_1(n), \chi_2(n))$.

¹Note that Cases A and B overlap. However, it is only important that Cases A, B, and C cover all the possibilities.

We claim that in the 6-coloring χ of \mathbb{N} there are no x, y , and z , all of the same color and $v_p(t_x x + t_y y + t_z z) > \max\{v_p(t_x x), v_p(t_y y), v_p(t_z z)\}$. Indeed, otherwise (by Lemma 2) we have $v_p(t_x x) = v_p(t_y y) \leq v_p(t_z z)$; or $v_p(t_x x) = v_p(t_z z) \leq v_p(t_y y)$; or $v_p(t_y y) = v_p(t_z z) \leq v_p(t_x x)$. If $v_p(t_x x) = v_p(t_y y)$, then $d + v_p(x) = v_p(y)$, hence, $\chi_1(x) \neq \chi_1(y)$, which contradicts $\chi(x) = \chi(y)$. If $v_p(t_x x) = v_p(t_z z)$, then $d + v_p(x) = v_p(z)$, hence, $\chi_1(x) \neq \chi_1(z)$, which contradicts $\chi(x) = \chi(z)$. So, assume that $v_p(t_y y) = v_p(t_z z) \leq v_p(t_x x)$. Recalling our coefficients, we obtain $v_p(y) = v_p(z) \leq d + v_p(x)$. By (the second part of) Lemma 2, we also have $v_p(2y - z) = d + v_p(x)$. Let e denote the common value of $v_p(y)$ and $v_p(z)$. Let $y = y'p^e$ and $z = z'p^e$. Since $\chi_2(y) = \chi_2(z)$, then $\chi_2'(y' \bmod p) = \chi_2'(z' \bmod p)$, hence, $2y' - z' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. However, this implies $v_p(2y - z) = e$, so $v_p(y) = v_p(z) = e = d + v_p(x)$. It follows from here that $\chi_1(x)$ is different from $\chi_1(y)$ and $\chi_1(z)$, which contradicts $\chi(x) = \chi(y) = \chi(z)$.

Since $v_p(0) = +\infty$ and there are no x, y, z , all of the same color and $v_p(t_x x + t_y y + t_z z) > \max\{v_p(t_x x), v_p(t_y y), v_p(t_z z)\}$, then, in particular, there are no monochromatic solutions to $t_x x + t_y y + t_z z = 0$ (i.e. $(b - 2a)x + 2y - z = 0$) in χ . Case B is essentially equivalent to Lemma 6 (with $s = 1$) in [4].

Notice that one can define χ_2 to be a 2-coloring in the proof above, as long as the order of 2 mod p is even.

Case C. $t_x \in \{-2, -1, 1, 2\}$

Case $t_x = -1$ is taken care of in [10], as mentioned before, while cases $t_x = 1$ and $t_x = -2$ correspond to Cases 1 and 2, respectively. The only remaining case is $t_x = 2$.² In this case, we have $y = ax + d$ and $z = (2a + 2)x + 2d$. Therefore, $2y < z < 4y$. Using Lemma 1, we obtain $\text{dor}(a, 2a + 2) \leq \lceil \log_2 4 \rceil = 2$. Hence, for all positive integers a , we have $\text{dor}(a, 2a + 2) = 2$. □

3. Concluding remarks

As a consequence of our proof, we obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dor}(1, 3) &= 2, \quad \text{dor}(2, 5) = 2, \quad \text{dor}(2, 6) = 2, \\ \text{dor}(3, 3) &\leq 3, \quad \text{dor}(3, 4) \leq 3, \quad \text{dor}(3, 8) = 2. \end{aligned}$$

These results improve the corresponding entries in the table provided by Landman and Robertson [10] for small values of a and b .

After submission, we learned that Frantzikinakis, Landman, and Robertson [5] independently showed that $\text{dor}(a, b)$ is finite unless $(a, b) = (1, 1)$.

²The equation is not regular in this case, however this possibility is not covered by Cases A and B of the improved upper bound analysis.

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